

FIZIKAVIY QONUNIYATLARNI TIRIK ORGANIZMDAGI JARAYONLARGA TADBIIQ ETISH .

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ANNOSTATSIYA.

Fizikaviy qonuniyatlar, fizika ilmi asosida o'rganilgan qonunlar va prinsiplar, tirik organizmdagi jarayonlarga ham ko'plab ta'sir qiladi. Bu qonuniyatlar, biologik jarayonlar, kimyoviy reaksiyalar, va boshqa fiziologik tizimlarda o'tkaziladigan jarayonlarni tushunarliroq tushuntirishga yordam beradi. Termoqonuniyatlar, energiya almashish va energiya yo'qotish jarayonlarini tushuntiradi. Biologik organizmlar, harakatlanish, issiqlik sarflash va boshqa faoliyatlar uchun energiya talab qiladi. Termoqonuniyatlar, organizmlar uchun zarur energiya miqdorini aniqlashda yordam beradi. Elektromagnit qonuniyatlar, elektrik to'qimalarining, signalning o'tkazilishini tushuntirilishini o'rganadi. Bu qonuniyatlar, sinapslarda (nerv oqimlarining aloqador joylari) elektrik signalning o'tkazilishini va organizmning faoliyati uchun zarur bo'lgan axborotni uzatishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Mexanika qonunlari, kuchlar, momentlar, va jarayonlarning tizimlari haqida ma'lumot beradi. Bu qonuniyatlar, tirik organizmlarda harakat, osilatsiya (tiklanish), va strukturani saqlash jarayonlarini tushuntirishda muhimdir. Biologik tizimlarda, optik prinsiplar, ko'z tuzilishi, fotosentez jarayonlarda muhim o'rin oladi. Atom va molekulalar fizikasi, kimyoviy reaksiyalarni, molekulalar o'rni va molekulalar orasidagi almashishlarni tushuntiradi. Bu jarayonlar, biologik tizimlarda modda almashinuvi va kimyoviy jarayonlar uchun muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: fiziologik tizim, termoqonuniyat, elektromagnit, struktura.

Biologik tizimlarning mexanik xususiyatlarini o'rganish va tushuntirishga bag'ishlangan bo'limdir. Bu maydon, organizmlarning harakatlanishi, tizimlarning mexanik ko'rsatkichlari, va biologik strukturani o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi. Misol uchun, biomexanika, hayvonlarning harakatlarini, tizimlarning mexanik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. Biofizika, organizmlarning issiqlik almashish va sarflash jarayonlarini o'rganadi. Bu, organizmlarning issiqlik regulyatsiyasi, issiqlik tarqatish jarayonlarini tushuntirishda muhimdir. Misol uchun, organizmlar qanday issiqlik sarflashni, issiqlik tarqatish tizimlari qanday ishlaydiganligini o'rganishga yordam beradi.

Elektrofizika, organizmlarning elektrik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. Bu, sinapslarda (nerv oqimlarining aloqador joylarida) elektrik impulslarining o'tkazilishini va organizmlarning fiziologik tizimlari bo'yicha elektrik aktivligini o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi. Biooptika, biologik tizimlarning optik xususiyatlarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Bu bo'limda ko'zning tuzilishi, fotosintez jarayonlari, va biologik strukturani optika yordamida tushuntirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Tirik organizmlar fizikasi, biologik tizimlarning qanday qonuniyatlarga asoslanganligini va bu qonuniyatlar bilan qanday shaklda amalga oshirilishini tushuntiradi

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Fizika qonunlarining inson organizmiga ta'siri juda kengdir. Inson organizmi va boshqa tirik organizmlar, bir nechta fizika qonuniyatlariga muvofiq harakat qiladi va ularga bog'liqdir. Quyidagi qonuniyatlar inson organizmi uchun ahamiyatli bo'lib hisoblanadi. Termodinamika qonuniyatlari, energiyaning almashishini, sarflashini va yo'qotilishini tushuntiradi. Inson organizmi ham har kuni energiya almashishi kerak. Bu qonuniyatlar, qanday qilib organizm issiqlikni saqlab qolishi va undan foydalanishi, shu bilan birga qanday qilib harakatga energiya sarflashini o'rganadi. Mexanika qonuniyatlari, kuchlar, momentlar, va tizimlar orasidagi ta'sirni o'rganadi. Inson organizmi ham harakatlanish va turli mexanik kuchlarga qarshi turadi. Masalan, biomexanika, inson harakatlarini o'rganishda foydalaniladi. Elektromagnit qonuniyatlari, elektrik va magnit kuchlarining o'tkazilishini tushuntiradi. Inson organizmi, nerv tizimi orqali elektrik signalini Bu va boshqa fizika qonuniyatlari inson organizmiga kuchli ta'sir qiladi va insonning hayoti va faoliyati uchun muhimdir. Termodinamika, issiqlik, energiya va ta'sir ko'rsatish (termodinamik tizimlarning birinchi qonuniyati) qonuniyatlari to'plami bo'lib, bu qonuniyatlar inson organizmi va boshqa tirik organizmlarga ta'sir qiladi. Quyidagi termodinamik qonuniyatlarning inson organizmiga ta'siri keng jihatdan o'rganilgan: Birinchi termodinamik qonuniyat, energiya almashish va sarflashni ta'rifi va chegaralari bilan bog'liqdir. Inson organizmi, har kuni energiya almashish va sarflash jarayonlarini amalga oshiradi. Yemek orqali energiya olish, harakatlanish, havo o'zgarishlariga moslashuvchanlik, va boshqa faoliyatlar, inson organizmi uchun energiya almashish va sarflashni ko'rsatkichlardir. Issiqlik ko'chirish, organizmning ichki strukturani muhofaza qilish, fiziologik faoliyatni saqlash va normal holatda qolish uchun muhimdir. Inson organizmi, issiqlik ko'chirish tizimlari orqali yuqori va past issiqlikli muhitlar orasida issiqlik almashishini va qat'iyanz issiqlikni ta'sir qilmasdan yo'qotishini

boshqaradi. Inson organizmining mustahkamligi, tizimlarning va organlarning o'zaro moslashishi, ularning faoliyati, va tibbiyotning umumiy holati orqali aniqlanadi. Bu mustahkamlik bir nechta faktorlar bilan bog'liqdir: Inson organizmi, immun tizim yordamida tibbiyotda mavjud zararli mikroblar, viruslar, va patogenlar bilan kurashadi. Immun tizim, antitoxinlar va antikorlar orqali organizmni muhofaza qiladi va kuchliroq mikroblar bilan kurashishga yordam beradi. Fizikaviy aktivlik va sport, inson organizmini mustahkamlaydi. Regulyar harakatlanish va fizikaviy mexanizmlar orqali, organizmning kuchli bo'lishi, og'riq va kasalliklar, yuqori qon bosimi, kardiologik muammolar, va o'z ichiga qanday qilib umumiy kasallik omillarini kamaytiradi. Inson tanasidagi mexanik harakatlar, biomexanika deb ataladigan fiziologik prinsiplar asosida o'rganiladi. Yurish, inson tanasidagi eng asosiy mexanik harakatlardan biridir. Yurish, qadam- qadam o'tkaziladi va biror maqsadga yuzaga keladi. Bu faoliyat inson tanasidagi tizimlarining ishlab chiqarishini va energetikani talab qiladi. Mexanik ish bajarish inson tanasidagi boshqa bir muhim mexanik harakatdir. Bu, ko'kraklar, qo'l va boshqa organlarni ishga tushirish orqali bajariladi. Mexanik ish uning boshqarish va modellashtirish qobiliyatiga ega bo'lgan ko'krak va muskullar tizimlari orqali amalga oshiriladi. Inson tanasidagi fiziologik faoliyatlar va harakatlar asosida o'rganiladi. Inson tanasidagi issiq va sovuq tanasidagi almashish va yo'qotish jarayonlarini boshqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan organ va tizimlardir. Bu a'zolar, issiq almashish va yo'qotishni ta'minlash, tizimlarni normal holatda saqlash, va tananing ichki muhitini barqaror va barqaror saqlashda katta ahamiyatga ega. Dermis, yoki teri, inson tanasining issiq almashish va yo'qotish jarayonlarini boshqaradi. Teri orqali, organizmning ichki muhitini barqaror saqlash, temperatura regulatsiyasida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Inson tanasidagi issiq va sovuq o'lchamlar, o'zaro bog'lanishlar orqali issiqlik almashish va yo'qotish jarayonlarini o'zlashtiradi. Bu o'lchamlar, issiqning muqobilini yechish uchun kerakli modifikatsiyalar bilan o'zgaradi. Inson tanasidagi yengil organlar, issiq va sovuq o'lchamlarni sezib olish, o'zgartirish va tanani yo'qotish jarayonlarini boshqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ular, organizmning tizimlarini optimal holatda saqlash va organizmni har xil muhit o'rtasidagi temperaturani qabul qilishda qo'llaniladi. Muskullar tizim, organizmning faoliyatlarini bajarishda yordam beradi va bu faoliyatlar issiq almashish va yo'qotishni boshqarishni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Bu a'zolar, inson tanasidagi issiq va sovuq almashish va yo'qotishni boshqarishda katta muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ularning to'g'ri faoliyati, organizmning normal holatda

saqlanishi, immun tizimni kuchli qilish va asosiy faoliyatlarni muhofaza qilish uchun zarurdir.

Xulosa.

Ma'lumotlarni amaliyotga o'tkazish, analiz qilish, va tahlil qilish uchun samarali texnikaviy asboblardan va vositalarni ishlatishni o'z ichiga oladi. Quyidagi bir nechta mashhur misollar keltirilgan: MRI (Magnit rezonans tomografiya): MRI, asosan tibbiyot sohasida ishlatiladi va organizmning ichki tuzilishi va holatini tasvirlash uchun, biologik ma'lumotlarni fizikaviy asbob yordamida olishda qo'llaniladi. Bu usul yordamida, tananing ichki organlari va tuzilishlari yaxshi ko'rsatiladi va tashxis qilishda, davolashda va tibbiyot ilmiy tadqiqotlarda keng qo'llaniladi. CT (Kompyuterli tomografiya): CT skannerlar, tananing ichki qismi va tuzilishi haqida ma'lumotlar olishda ham foydalaniladi. Tomografik tasvirlar hosil qiladi va tibbiyotda inson tanasining muammolarini diagnoz etishda va davolashda qo'llaniladi. (Ultratovush tahlili): Ultratovush tahlili, biologik tuzilish va harakatlanishni tasvirlash va tahlil qilishda juda samarali bo'lib, uzluksiz va zararli xususiyatlarga ega. Bu usul, tanadagi organlarning qanday qilib ishlashini va harakatlarini o'rganishda, shuningdek, diagnostik tibbiyotda turli kasalliklar va muammolar haqida ma'lumot olishda yordam beradi. Laboratoriya asboblari: Tibbiy laboratoriyalarda ishlatiladigan bir nechta texnikaviy asboblardan, biologik ma'lumotlarni olishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Misol uchun, kimyoviy indikatorlarni o'rganishda keng qo'llaniladi. Elektrokardiografiya (EKG): EKG, yurakning elektrik faoliyatini o'rganishda foydalaniladi va yurak funksiyasini va harakatlarini tahlil qilishda samarali bo'lib, tibbiyot tizimlarining normal yoki patologik holatini tushuntiradi. Biologik va tibbiy ma'lumotlarni olishda foydalaniladigan bir nechta fizik-texnikaviy asboblardan va vositalardir. Ular, tibbiyotda tuzilish va funksiyalarni o'rganish, tibbiyot tadqiqotlari va tibbiyot davolash uchun muhimdir. Organizmning a'zo va to'qimalarining faoliyati asosida yotuvchi umumiy fizikaviy va biofizikaviy qonuniyatlar, biologiya va fizikaning ko'p tomondan integratsiyasini o'z ichiga oladi. Energiyaning saqlanishi va o'zgarishi organizmdagi barcha kimyoviy va fizikaviy harakatlarni, harakatlanishni va ish faoliyatini energiya almashish va yo'qotish jarayonlariga bog'liq bo'lib, biologik sistemalarni tanlashda muhimdir. Bu qonuniyatlar, optik va optoelektronika vositalari orqali organizmning optik tashqi va ichki strukturasi haqida ma'lumot olishda yordam beradi.

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